

Transforming Library Operations: The Importance of ICT in Streamlining Services and Management

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ABSTRACT

This research paper attempts to explore the critical role, impact, and importance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the management and provision of library services and its impact on the present-day scenario. ICT is a term used in libraries to refer to the use of computers and other technologies in library practices such as acquisition, storage, organization, and dissemination of information. The world has become a global village, and with ICT, many library users now have access to a vast sea of information without spending much time or energy. The process of general and information distribution is now being facilitated by the use of ICT. ICT includes the range of technologies used to support communication and information dissemination. This paper identified the challenges of ICT application in libraries. Among others, it was recommended that the capacity and level of adoption by libraries should be improved. This paper attempts to capture the wider benefits of ICT in library use.

Keywords: *Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Libraries, Library Services, Institutions, and Organizations.*

INTRODUCTION

Information Communication Technology (ICT) has been a catalyst for national progress and information issues, as power is effectively an unlimited resource and an essential resource for the development of all sectors in a nation. Therefore, it is necessary to imperative application libraries in a proper manner. To fulfill the information needs of citizens. It is worth noting that the growth of ICT has had a huge impact on the quality of information provided by libraries. It enables proper and adequate provision of library services to library users in all branches. In this 21st century, the role of ICT in library operations can become more important. Many library outline sand operations which were initially done manually are now being converted into computerized operations which means, ICT techniques are used to provide better and faster services to the end users. A nation without a functional library and information center may lack information that would enable its sustainable development. In this age of globalization, in which the world is connected, information derives its power through permanent storage and wide distribution, which can be achieved through ICT. The use of ICT improves access to digital information, reduces the digital divide and improves quality of life. The adoption of ICT in libraries is far from improving the information services provided in libraries. This is an era, when people need to access timely information easily and

this can be done through the application of ICT to library services. This is one way to contribute to the sustainable development of the nation; Timely and effective provision of useful information can help build society as an enabling tool ICT can help libraries in the provision of information, which is very important for the development of various sectors of the nation. Using ICT, libraries are playing a very important role in accessing global information and knowledge resources. Apparently, ICTs are indispensable tools required for the provision of value-added information that supports sustainable development. Many organizations and institutions, including libraries, face various challenges in the process of integrating ICT into their services. Yet, provision of information is paramount for the development and growth of any nation. It is therefore important that efforts be made to enable the use of ICT in all sectors of the country, ICT and library services.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the various components of ICT in the provision of library services.
2. Emphasizing the benefits of ICT in libraries.
3. To study the challenges faced by libraries in implementation of ICT.
4. To make recommendations for improving ICT in libraries.
5. To study the impact and importance of ICT in the provision of library services.

COMPONENTS OF ICT IN THE PROVISION OF LIBRARY SERVICES

The advent of ICT has really boosted library services as it now helps many librarians to reach out to library users using their ICT capabilities. Some of the ICT-based services that are provided by libraries are as follows:

Provision of web access to OPAC: Libraries are providing access to a web-based online public access catalog (OPAC) interface. OPAC makes it easy for users to access and use information resources. OPAC is a computerized format of library catalog for accessing library materials.

Electronic Document Delivery: An ICT-based interlibrary lending system, implemented by libraries through the use of electronic networks for document distribution. In short, Document Delivery Services (DDS) enable libraries to access copies of research papers or other research documents, from other libraries. These documents can be journal articles or other documents in digital form. They are primarily in Portable Document Format (PDF) and are delivered to library users' desktops.

Network Information Resources: Libraries now provide users with access to network information such as databases, electronic scholarly journals and other publications from various publishers. These services provided in a library vary from one library to another depending on the type of library, the type of patrons and the objectives of the parent institution. Other library services highlighted include:

- Technical Services
- Current Awareness Services (CAS)
- Selective Dissemination of Information(SDI)
- Reference Service
- Reprographic Service

- Serials Control
- Borrowing, Renewing, and Reserving
- Computerized Interactive Search
- Exhibition and Display

Reprographic Technology: It is widely used in libraries worldwide. Reprographic machines are provided in the library to facilitate photocopying of documents on demand.

Library Retrieval System: This involves using compact disc read-only memory (CDROM), a technological mechanism for acquiring specialized CD-ROM databases in various disciplines, such as law, sciences, medicine, technology, agriculture, and humanities.

Indexing and Abstracting Services: This service provides summaries of documents and assigns descriptors for referencing documents.

Institutional Repository: This is an online repository for collecting, preserving, and disseminating digital copies of the intellectual output of academic or research institutions, which may be journal articles as well as digital versions of theses and dissertations. This service is mainly provided in academic or research libraries.

Document Scanning Services: Scanners are an important tool in library modernization. It is useful for scanning text, images, and content pages of books and establishing a digital and virtual library.

BENEFITS OF ICT IN LIBRARIES

Globalization driven by ICT is currently having an unprecedented impact on library practices. ICTs are important and useful tools for sustainable development in all sectors and in all aspects of our society. ICTs provide the means to achieve developmental goals in other sectors, including education, health, agriculture, business, and commerce. The introduction of ICT in education led to the computerization of traditional materials such as library books, journals, newspapers, and other information resources. This has also given rise to the existence of virtual library libraries. Academic researchers, through the use of ICT, can easily access current literature. ICTs also encourage collaboration among researchers regardless of their location.

The Internet provides updated information on any subject. Similarly, previous research findings can be easily obtained through the Internet. In the agricultural sector, ICT is being used to provide inputs to farmers in terms of their plants and animals, thereby increasing their productivity.

In professional duties, computers are used to automate various manual tasks. Editing, cataloging, circulation of library materials Cataloging, circulation, and serial management of library materials are now automated in libraries using software available in the market. ICT enables libraries to search, store, retrieve, and disseminate information. ICT tools like CD-ROM CD-ROM Dissemination of information. In addition, digitization of information resources, which includes converting print resources into electronic format, is also done using ICT.

ICT in libraries also offers the following advantages:

- Fast and simple access to information and remote and 24/7 user access.
- ICT helps library operations be simpler, quicker, cheaper, and more effective.
- Providing unlimited access to information from multiple sources.
- ICT helps manage information overload as information retrieval becomes easier in computerized systems.
- Computerization helps speed up reading and paper reduction of libraries.

There is no doubt that the integration of ICT in the provision of library services is capable of bringing great benefits to the entire society and the nation. ICT, which is an enabling tool for the provision of timely and current library and information services, is also indispensable for sustainable development. ICT can be applied to every aspect of human endeavors to provide services that deliver results. The use of ICT tools enables organizations and institutions to provide services more effectively.

CHALLENGES WITH USING ICT TO PROVISION LIBRARY SERVICES

It is recognized that the adoption and use of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in libraries have many benefits; however, there are many challenges to be faced. This includes:

- **Limited Financial Resources:** Acquisition and maintenance of relevant equipment depends on the availability of funds. Mainly, many libraries lack the funds that enable them to acquire the necessary ICT to connect to the Internet, subscribe to various online databases, and acquire software licenses.
- **Shortage of ICT facilities and ICT skills:** Computers are used to access and store large amounts of information. Similarly, Internet accessibility is made possible through the use of computers and they are used to access the Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) and perform many other routine library activities. Lack of computers and other facilities is a major challenge faced by many libraries. Many librarians also lack ICT skills and this makes it difficult for them to adopt technological innovations. Lack of ICT skills severely restricts the use of ICT for the provision of library services. When ICT policies are not available or implemented adequately, they can affect the sustainability of a nation's development.
- **Lack of ICT policies:** Developing countries lack a systematic ICT policy, and this hinders the deployment of ICT.
- **Poor maintenance of ICT equipment:** Many libraries lack space and a conducive environment to keep ICT equipment. In addition, ICT equipment is not adequately maintained in most libraries as maintenance costs are usually very high.
- **Erratic electricity supply:** In developing countries, large areas still have unreliable electricity supply.

The other challenges are:

- Lack of technical knowledge from library staff.
- Insufficient bandwidth.

- Constant changes in software and hardware.
- Copyright and Intellectual Property Rights Management.

CONCLUSION

The use of ICT for library services is an important effort for the sustainable development of the country. Therefore, libraries must strive to provide the right information at the right time, in order to remain agents of sustainable development. With the advent of ICT, the objectives of libraries will not only be achieved but it will also help libraries to compete with their counterparts in the developed world. Developing countries should also recognize ICT as a key strategic tool for sustainable development. Institutions, including libraries, should be supported and encouraged to adopt and use ICT to provide efficient and effective services to institutions.

Recommendations

In consideration of the findings above, it is recommended that:

- Libraries should be regularly funded. All libraries, regardless of type, need strong financial support from a parent institution.
- Standardized provision of stand by generators in libraries to supply computers and other ICT facilities in case of power failure. Besides, the government should make efforts to permanently solve the challenges especially in the power sector.
- Librarians must become highly systems thinkers and fully equip themselves to work in digital and computer environments.
- Government should provide and ensure that libraries are provided with ICT tools for effective library functions and information dissemination.
- Policies promoting the deployment and development of ICT in all institutions should be formulated and implemented to sustain the development of the nation.
- Government should make library and information services a part of national development initiatives and schemes.
- Training and retraining of all categories of library staff should be conducted regularly. ICT largely depends on the ability of employees to operate ICT facilities. The training should include the skills and techniques required to input data into a computer, surf the Internet, and use various telecommunication facilities to exchange information.

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